

Regularized reconciliation of hierarchical forecasts with application to building electricity demand

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Hierarchical forecasting
Reconciliation
Regularization
Machine learning
Neural networks
Building management

ABSTRACT

Hierarchical forecasting plays a critical role in advancing building energy systems by ensuring coherence across different levels of aggregation, such as individual rooms, building floors, and entire facilities. While traditional reconciliation approaches, such as bottom-up and top-down methods, offer simplicity, they often ignore valuable information across hierarchical levels, leading to myopic and biased forecasts. Recent advances have introduced machine learning into hierarchical forecasting to improve accuracy and allow for more flexibility. In this study, we propose a novel reconciliation framework that builds on neural networks and is tailored to electricity demand forecasting in buildings. We introduce a set of loss functions that penalize incoherence across various hierarchical relationships, including discrepancies between adjacent levels and between the top and bottom levels. Our method employs a global model that simultaneously generates and reconciles forecasts across the hierarchy, thereby eliminating the need for independent base forecasts and enabling cross-series learning. We validate our method using electricity consumption data from a modern office building in Helsinki, Finland. Results demonstrate that our approach outperforms standard reconciliation methods and achieves a significant loss reduction in terms of both accuracy and coherence in complex, multi-level building settings. The results translate into practical benefits that can be used to improve building energy management by enabling more accurate load shifting, enhanced scheduling of HVAC operations and improved utilization of on-site renewable generation, all of which highlight the utility of the approach in complex, real-world energy forecasting applications.

1. Introduction

As global energy demand continues to grow, awareness of energy consumption has become more critical than ever, especially in the building sector [1]. Buildings account for approximately 40% of the global energy consumption and associated emissions [2], where a substantial amount of this energy usage is attributed to heating, cooling, lighting, and equipment operation [3]. Thus, effective management strategies are imperative to reduce waste, lower operational costs, and meet sustainability goals [4]. Energy forecasting is a crucial asset among these strategies, as it enables proactive, data-driven decision-making. More accurate forecasts enable the effective anticipation of energy needs, which paves the way for better operation of building systems, efficient load planning, and intelligent integration of renewable energy sources [5,6]. However, as buildings grow in size and complexity, and as sensors are deployed to monitor everything from overall energy consumption down to indi-

vidual uses and appliances, forecasting approaches must also adapt to seamlessly handle multiple levels of data and provide coherent results across the hierarchy that the involved systems and spaces define. In this context, hierarchical forecasting poses a significant advantage, since it generates accurate forecasts that are consistent across different levels of aggregation.

In energy forecasting, aggregation occurs in a variety of settings. For instance, regional electricity demand consolidates into national electricity demand [7], while a building's total energy consumption represents the sum of individual uses across different spaces [8]. Base forecasts at each aggregation level may serve distinct purposes and support different decisions, and are frequently generated independently using different models. This has led to the growing popularity of hierarchical forecasting, which addresses the need for coherence and improved accuracy in such multi-level settings. The utility of hierarchical forecasting is twofold. First, it ensures that management decisions are taken on

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2025.116711>

Received 8 August 2025; Received in revised form 13 October 2025; Accepted 8 November 2025

Available online 13 November 2025

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the basis of coherent forecasts, thereby ensuring consistency. Second, it improves forecast accuracy by integrating information from across the hierarchy [9]. Consequently, it enables building and facility managers to exercise precise control at granular levels and make more informed operational decisions [10], while maintaining alignment with higher-level objectives such as energy budgeting, load shifting, and coordination with utility providers. Collectively, these benefits foster a more reliable decision-making environment and strengthen both management and operational strategies.

To illustrate, consider a university campus comprising multiple buildings, each equipped with sub-metering at the floor or appliance level. At the lowest level, forecasts of HVAC or lighting energy use support local control strategies such as occupancy-based scheduling or real-time load adjustment. At the building level, facility managers rely on aggregate energy forecasts to plan demand response events, optimize chiller operation, or manage battery storage systems. Moving up the hierarchy, the campus or the energy community it belongs to aggregates these forecasts to inform energy procurement, budgeting, or participation in flexibility markets. If forecasts at these different levels are generated independently and are not coherent, then decision-making becomes inconsistent. Local optimization might conflict with global objectives, leading to inefficient resource allocation, over- or under-estimation of total demand, and potentially higher operational costs.

Traditionally, hierarchical forecasting has been conducted using single-level approaches, such as the bottom-up (BU), top-down (TD) or middle-out (MO) methods. In these methods, base forecasts are produced for a selected level, which are then either summed up to forecast the higher levels of the hierarchy or disaggregated using proper weights (proportions) to forecast the lower levels [11]. While straightforward, single-level approaches ignore valuable information available at other levels, often leading to myopic and biased forecasts [12]. Comparative studies of these methods have shown mixed results, concluding that performance may vary significantly depending on data characteristics, series correlation, and aggregation level considered, among others [13]. In this regard, research focus has moved toward methods that exploit the complete set of base forecasts, realized initially by applying ordinary least squares reconciliation [14] and later by employing scaled reconciliation [15], which assigns different weights to each base forecast based on the level it refers to or its relative accuracy. Other modifications have introduced the addition of optimization constraints, such as generating non-negative reconciled forecasts [16] or retaining some of the base forecasts unchanged [17], and the introduction of resistance-based estimators that shrink the effect of outliers on reconciliation weights [18].

The rise of machine learning (ML) inspired a new wave of hierarchical forecasting methods. Multiple studies have sought to replace linear regression with more flexible approaches, aiming to combine base forecasts more effectively. An initial approach towards this direction involved using tree-based regression models, tasked with generating forecasts for the lowest level of the hierarchy based on the base forecasts available for all aggregation levels [19]. The new bottom-level forecasts are then aggregated in a BU fashion to ensure coherence. Apart from enabling a selective, non-linear combination of the base forecasts, this approach has the advantage that the models are trained with the objective of minimizing forecast error, in contrast to standard reconciliation methods, where any performance improvement is a welcome side effect of the forecast ensembling taking place. Another approach considered the use of an encoder-decoder neural network, where the encoder is tasked with mapping the base forecasts to the bottom level reconciled forecasts, while the decoder takes the latter as input and reconstructs the forecasts at all levels [20]. ML methods have also been adopted to disaggregate upper-level forecasts into lower levels using estimated proportions [21]. Other approaches have focused on the optimal selection of standard reconciliation methods based on the particularities of the hierarchy and the series it comprises [22].

An interesting stream of research has focused on modifying the objective function used by ML models to derive reconciled forecasts [23–25].

In brief, rather than solely minimizing the forecast error, a regularization term is introduced to the models' loss function to account for incoherence and formulate reconciled forecasts accordingly. A benefit of this approach is that the ML model, which is typically a neural network, can produce reconciled forecasts directly without necessarily requiring the provision of base forecasts. Moreover, since a global model is trained across multiple series to generate the forecasts, accuracy improvements are expected due to the cross-learning effect [26]. The disadvantage of this approach is that it does not guarantee coherence since regularization only penalizes incoherent forecasts, serving as a soft constraint. Consequently, the reconciled forecasts of the lowest level must practically be aggregated through a BU strategy to ensure strict coherence. The main variation among methods following this approach effectively lies on how regularization is applied and at which levels the forecasts are produced, with some methods focusing on the downward disaggregation of higher-level forecasts [27] and others on the integration of upper-level information to the bottom-level forecasts [28].

Hierarchical forecasting has naturally found several applications within the energy domain. In wind power forecasting, [29] exploited the cross-sectional and temporal hierarchical structure of turbines to improve accuracy, while [30] leveraged temporal correlation to reconcile hierarchical wind power forecasts both optimally and efficiently. In the solar power context, [31] introduced a spatio-temporal point forecast reconciliation approach to generate non-negative, fully coherent forecasts. For district heating load forecasting, [32] proposed a hierarchical reconciliation of convolutional gated recurrent units to unify load forecasts and enhance point and interval forecast accuracy. In electricity load forecasting specifically, hierarchical methods have been studied across diverse settings and methodological perspectives. Early work by [33] introduced a framework that combines the bottom-up approach with hierarchical linear models for long-term electricity consumption forecasting [8]. investigated the effect of cross-temporal aggregation using data from five bank branches, employing multiple aggregation levels to mitigate modelling uncertainty before applying standard single-level reconciliation approaches. Extending the treatment of temporal hierarchies, [34] assessed an enhanced reconciliation scheme that explicitly accounts for both auto- and cross-correlation structures, using hourly load data from the Nord Pool electricity market. The same data were later used by [35] to evaluate a dimensionality reduction technique that enables informed reconciliation without estimating the full cross-covariance matrix [36]. examined three hierarchical forecasting strategies—aggregating information at the pre-forecasting, model-building, and post-forecasting stages—based on load data from 13 university buildings, highlighting the trade-offs between model complexity and forecast performance. Beyond deterministic settings, some studies have explored probabilistic approaches [37]. and [38] investigated hierarchical probabilistic forecasting, using UK residential smart meter data and employing cross-validation and sampling-based reconciliation to improve calibration and coherence, respectively. To enhance robustness to estimation errors during reconciliation, [39] developed a sparse adjustment algorithm formulated as a high-dimensional penalized regression, which preserves aggregation constraints while reducing noise in the adjustment process [40]. conducted a comparative study of probabilistic and hierarchical forecasting methods for predicting electrical loads at secondary substations and cabinets in low-voltage distribution grids, finding that specific reconciliation strategies yielded superior results. Finally, a game-theoretically optimal reconciliation framework, guaranteed to improve any given set of forecasts, was proposed by [41] and demonstrated on both simulated and real electricity consumption data from France.

To summarize, despite the progress made in the field, most implementations have been limited to the use of standard, linear reconciliation methods or variations of them, largely ignoring the benefits that ML can offer in terms of both accuracy and flexibility. The relevant research conducted in the area of energy use in buildings is even more scarce, since despite the variety of existing approaches, current electric-

Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed method illustrating how the training process is driven by both forecast error and hierarchical incoherence.

ity demand forecasting methods face key challenges when extended to hierarchical or multi-level settings. More specifically, standard methods such as SARIMA, exponential smoothing and regression-based models are suitable for single-level series, but when applied in multi-level settings, they cannot capture and enforce hierarchical coherence without external support. Traditional reconciliation methods are usually applied on top to improve structural coherence, however, the process remains static and decoupled from the training process. ML-based approaches on the other hand, are able to model complex, non-linear relationships on large datasets and should be further explored, since they are typically trained independently for each level or series in building settings. These limitations explain why existing methodologies often underperform in multi-level and complex electricity demand forecasting.

To address these limitations, this study explores the potential of ML-based forecast reconciliation for building electricity demand, as follows:

- We extend the work done on regularization for incoherence penalization in ML-based reconciliation by introducing a set of novel loss functions, each of which approaches the problem from a different angle. Accordingly, incoherence is measured by tracking the differences between the forecasts generated at a given level and the level below it, above it, or both. Moreover, we examine several loss functions that account for the differences between the top and bottom levels of the hierarchy in addition to those measured between consecutive levels, thereby offering a more insightful solution.
- We train a global neural network to simultaneously produce hierarchical forecasts and reconcile them, thus omitting the separate step of generating base forecasts while capitalizing on the advantages of cross-learning.
- The proposed method is demonstrated using a comprehensive dataset that records the electricity consumption of a modern office building in Helsinki, Finland, comprising sixty-nine rooms organized into eight floors and three sections. Given the size and diversity of the energy uses and spatial configurations in the hierarchy, we benchmark our reconciliation approach against standard methods under a challenging yet real-world setup.

By integrating the reconciliation process directly into model training, the proposed design allows the joint optimization of coherence across the hierarchy. This integration allows information to flow throughout the hierarchy, enabling the model to dynamically adapt to complex energy patterns while enforcing hierarchical consistency from granular individual rooms to total building demand.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the proposed reconciliation method and the loss functions considered for penalizing incoherence. Section 3 describes the data used to demonstrate the proposed method. Section 4 provides details on the implementation of the model, including data preparation and training. Finally, Section 5 presents the results and discusses our main findings, while Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Proposed approach

The proposed method aims to ensure hierarchical coherence while maintaining high forecasting accuracy. Error propagation is a major drawback of traditional reconciliation methods, as poor forecast accuracy at one level can affect the entire hierarchy by spreading the bias across all levels when aggregating or disaggregating. To combat this, the proposed approach aims to combine individual series accuracy with hierarchy coherence loss to ensure consistency with related nodes. This is achieved through an integrated approach that embeds the reconciliation process directly into the training phase, rather than treating forecasting and reconciliation as separate steps. Thus, since each series forecast is optimized jointly with the hierarchy, individual over- or underestimation is penalized during training and cannot be transferred to other levels. This integration enhances information exchange across hierarchical levels and series, effectively balancing predictive performance with structural consistency.

The method begins by initializing a separate multilayer perceptron (MLP) for each time series within the hierarchy. These MLPs are trained in parallel, each computing its own *forecast accuracy loss*. This loss is then combined with a *coherence loss*, derived by considering the joint forecasts of multiple models. By incorporating an incoherence penalty into the training loop, the models receive real-time feedback on how well forecasts align across different hierarchical levels, allowing them to adjust their weights accordingly.

To better understand the impact of coherence loss on hierarchical alignment, three configurations inspired by traditional BU, TD, and MO reconciliation methods are evaluated, along with a fourth configuration based on a closed-loop approach. These experiments offer deeper insight into how the embedded coherence loss influences overall model performance. An overview of the proposed method is presented in Fig. 1.

A more detailed description of the approach is provided in the following algorithm: Assume a time series hierarchy comprising k levels and m series in total, each with n observations.

1. The time series are split into a training and test set, with the training set including observations up to a point $p < n$ in the series. The remaining observations $\{p, p+1, \dots, n\}$ are used for the test set.
2. Each series in the training set is assigned a separate MLP that is trained to produce forecasts, totalling m distinct MLPs.
3. During training, at each iteration, h -step-ahead forecasts are produced by each model, where h is the forecasting horizon.
4. Given the forecasts from the current iteration, a forecast accuracy loss is initially calculated, using the Mean Absolute Scaled Error (MASE) as a performance measure [42], defined as follows:

$$\text{MASE}(y, \bar{y}) = \frac{\frac{1}{h} \sum_{t=p+1}^{p+h} |y_t - \bar{y}_t|}{\frac{1}{p-s} \sum_{t=s+1}^p |y_t - y_{t-s}|}, \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2. Overview of the root-oriented approach when applied in its standard form versus its closed-loop form.

- in which y_t represents the observed value at period t , \bar{y}_t is the respective forecast, and s is the seasonal frequency of the data. This process is executed in parallel for all m models.
- The selected coherence loss is computed using the acquired forecasts in the current pass, penalizing the discrepancies between parent-child forecasts. Depending on the configuration and the time series, a different formula is used to measure the difference between the forecasts of two different hierarchical levels. The coherence loss approaches proposed are detailed in Section 2.1; however, in every case the difference is based on the MASE metric to ensure that the accuracy and the coherence losses are scale-independent, and can be combined without overpowering each other. By the end of this process m coherence losses are computed.
 - The accuracy and coherence losses calculated for each model are then summed, as shown in the following equation, and back-propagated. Through back-propagation, each series model's weights are adjusted not only to fit its own history, but to also maintain consistency with the hierarchy, thereby coupling all levels during training. This process is repeated in every new pass of the training process.

$$L^{(i)} = L_{Accuracy}^{(i)} + \lambda \cdot L_{Coherence}^{(i)} \quad (2)$$

where i represents each pass in the training process.

By the end of this process, each model is capable of producing forecasts that capture time series characteristics while simultaneously reducing inconsistencies between different levels.

2.1. Coherence loss

This section introduces the various coherence loss functions used in our study and motivates their adoption based on their logic and expected performance. In total, four different configurations are tested: three inspired by traditional reconciliation methods and one based on a closed-loop approach. The first three configurations focus on the differences between the forecasts produced at a certain level and the level below it (TD), above it (BU), or both (MO). The fourth approach on the other hand, accounts for the differences between the top and bottom levels of the hierarchy in addition to those measured between consecutive levels.

2.1.1. Root-Oriented

As the name implies, the first approach is heavily inspired by the TD reconciliation method, which leverages the forecasts of the highest level to reconcile the forecasts of the lower levels, effectively by disaggregating the former according to predefined proportions. Similarly, this loss function, $L_{Coherence-RO}$, penalizes the differences of a parent node and its child nodes to conform the latter to the former. Let $p(s_i)$ denote a non-leaf node and $c(p(s_i))$ the immediate child nodes of $p(s_i)$. The coherence loss measures the variation, using MASE, between the forecast of the parent node, $f_{p(s_i)}$, and the sum of the forecasts of the child nodes, $\sum_{s_j \in c(p(s_i))} f_{s_j}$, as follows:

$$L_{Coherence-RO} = \text{MASE}(f_{p(s_i)}, \sum_{s_j \in c(p(s_i))} f_{s_j}) \quad (3)$$

Observe that in this approach the root nodes are used as a reference, penalizing the child nodes accordingly. Therefore, the remaining levels are aggregated and compared against their direct parent node to calculate their coherence loss, meaning that child nodes under the same parent will have the same loss. The left diagram in Fig. 2 illustrates the root-oriented approach within a four-level hierarchy.

2.1.2. Leaf-Oriented

The next approach, $L_{Coherence-LO}$, is inspired by the BU reconciliation method, which uses forecasts from the lowest, most disaggregated level to reconcile the upper levels through aggregation. This loss function encourages the consistency between non-leaf nodes and their child nodes by penalizing their differences, as follows. Let $c(s_i)$ denote the direct child nodes of a non-leaf node s_i of the hierarchy. The loss is the MASE of the s_i forecast, assuming that the sum of the child node forecasts is the reference point, defined as:

$$L_{Coherence-LO} = \text{MASE}(\sum_{j \in c(s_i)} f_j, f_{s_i}) \quad (4)$$

Unlike the root-oriented approach, this configuration encourages the upper levels to align with the sum of the lower-level forecasts, thereby emphasizing the most granular time series. The left diagram in Fig. 3 illustrates the leaf-oriented approach within a four-level hierarchy.

Fig. 3. Overview of the leaf-oriented approach when applied in its standard form versus its closed-loop form.

2.1.3. Bi-Directional

This configuration employs a hybrid approach that starts at an intermediate level of the hierarchy and aggregates or disaggregates the corresponding forecasts to the adjacent levels to promote coherence. Following the same logic as before, this loss, $L_{Coherence-BD}$, allows levels to consider both parent and child nodes by penalizing the respective deviations. Let s_i denote a node that is neither a root nor a leaf. The loss encourages upward consistency by comparing the parent forecast $p(s_i)$ with the sum of its immediate children, which includes the s_i node and its siblings $s(p(s_i))$, and downward consistency by comparing the s_i forecasts with the sum of its children forecasts at $c(s_i)$, as follows:

$$L_{Coherence-BD} = \text{MASE}(f_{p(s_i)}, \sum_{j \in s(p(s_i))} f_j) + \text{MASE}(\sum_{k \in c(s_i)} f_k, f_{s_i}) \quad (5)$$

The approach effectively allows middle levels to act as hubs that enforce bi-directional coherence, promote more balanced forecasts, and facilitate information exchange between levels. The left diagram in Fig. 4 illustrates the bi-directional approach within a four-level hierarchy.

2.1.4. Closed-loop reconciliation

The final loss function evaluated involves a closed-loop approach that generalizes the three previous methods. It is motivated by the limitation of traditional reconciliation methods, in which the root and leaf nodes are defined as reference points and consequently remain unaffected in the reconciliation process. However, in many cases employing a circular approach that allows edge nodes to interact improves forecasting performance [14]. For instance, in the case of the leaf-oriented loss, the leaf nodes are used as reference points to penalize inconsistencies in the immediate upper layers. By applying a closed-loop approach, however, the bottom level can also interact with the top level to facilitate information exchange between levels that are not directly connected and allow for more flexibility, as illustrated in Fig. 3.

In the present study, this approach is applied and compared against all three previous loss functions to better understand the effect of cir-

cularity on the forecasting process. To distinguish our closed-loop approaches from the previous configurations, we use the following abbreviations: $L_{Coherence-CL-RO}$, $L_{Coherence-CL-LO}$ and $L_{Coherence-CL-BD}$.

Note that in all the configurations introduced above, the losses are computed across multiple levels. As a result, the actual loss of the network is calculated as the arithmetic mean of the individual losses. Alternatively, and when justified, one may consider a weighted average of the individual losses to place greater emphasis on certain comparisons. This adjustment may be particularly relevant in closed-loop reconciliation where the loss involving the top and bottom levels could be assigned greater weight than the remaining losses.

3. Case study

The dataset used to train and evaluate the hierarchical forecasting approaches proposed in this study originates from an office building located in Helsinki, Finland. The building was constructed in 2020 and is currently operated by the City of Helsinki. All the spaces were designed to foster collaboration among officials and, at the same time, to serve the citizens. The first two floors of the building primarily consist of public areas, while the upper floors are mainly used by the Urban Environment Division responsible for activities such as city planning, building supervision, and environmental services. The building encompasses an area of 35,261 m^2 and has eight floors, including seven above-ground floors and one basement. The substantial size of the building, in addition to its equipment with multiple sensors monitoring the energy consumption of various systems, makes it an ideal testbed to apply and test our forecasting methods and evaluate the potential of the described reconciliation approaches in producing more accurate forecasts across multiple hierarchical levels.

The building's spatial organization naturally supports hierarchical modeling. It is divided into three main sections, each comprising eight floors, which in turn include a total of 69 rooms. The hierarchical

Fig. 4. Overview of the bi-directional approach when applied in its standard form versus its closed-loop form.

organization of the building is depicted in Fig. 5 and is structured as follows:

- Level 0: Consists of 1 node, which includes the aggregation of the three sections at level 1.
- Level 1: Consists of 3 nodes, representing the different sections of the building. Each section consists of 8 floors.
- Level 2: Consists of 24 nodes (3 sections, each of 8 floors). Note that the floors do not contain a fixed number of rooms, instead, each floor contains a varying number of rooms.
- Level 3: Consists of 69 nodes, each representing the energy consumption of a room. This level represents the highest level of granularity.

The meters monitor four main energy uses: heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems, lighting, uninterruptible power supply (UPS), and other general appliances. Moreover, the total energy consumption is recorded for each room. Upon analysing the provided data, it was evident that there were discrepancies between the total energy consumption of the rooms and the sum of the subsystem values, revealing missing measurements or values that were not captured properly. Therefore, to ensure consistency and completeness, the architectural structure of the building was chosen as the basis for forming the hierarchy, using the total energy consumption monitored in each room as the most granular nodes. Nevertheless, the hierarchical forecasting methods demonstrated in our study can be applied to different hierarchies depending on the specific analytical focus.

An interesting observation made during the data analysis process is that the building’s time series exhibit significant variations across different rooms, both in terms of magnitude and usage patterns, as shown in Fig. 6. This inherently leads to energy consumption variations between rooms and entire floors, since they serve different functions. Such examples include kitchens, HVAC management rooms, and other specialized spaces that operate outside regular office schedules and functions. This non-uniformity, combined with the varying number of rooms on each floor, introduces a substantial level of complexity into the hierarchy. Consequently, it creates an ideal testing environment for the custom reconciliation approaches proposed in this study, where both the accuracy of individual series and the consistency across the hierarchy are crucial.

Regarding the characteristics of the individual time series, five months of continuous hourly measurements are available, covering the period from May to October of 2023. Earlier data points were excluded due to low quality, since extended periods were missing. This time frame

corresponds to a consistently warm season, which suggests that the energy consumption levels and usage of different systems, specifically for heating and cooling, remain stable and consistent. This dataset is used to train and test the forecasting models developed in this study.

4. Experimental setup

4.1. Data preparation

An important step of the implementation is the data preparation, to ensure the series can be effectively used by the models. To enable the evaluation of the models on unseen data, the dataset is first partitioned into training and test sets. Specifically, 80% of the data (4 months) is used for training the models and the remaining 20% (1 month) for their evaluation. The partitioning is performed in chronological order to simulate realistic forecasting scenarios and ensure that there is no information leakage. This means that the first $0.8 \times n$ observations are used for training and the remaining $0.2 \times n$ for testing, where n is the length of the time series.

To allow the time series to be processed efficiently by the MLP models, a rolling-window approach is used that moves a fixed-size window across the series, thereby creating all possible pairs of inputs and targets [26]. Assuming $\{y_i\}_{i=1}^n$ is a time series of length n , each possible input $\mathbf{X}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{lags}}$ consists of a fixed number of consecutive values, while the respective target output $\mathbf{Y}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{steps}}$ consists of the subsequent values that need to be predicted. The different pairs occur by incrementing the index and sliding a fixed-size window across the time series values. This is represented below:

$$\mathbf{X}_i = [y_i, y_{i+1}, \dots, y_{i+n_{lags}-1}] \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{Y}_i = [y_{i+n_{lags}}, y_{i+n_{lags}+1}, \dots, y_{i+n_{lags}+n_{steps}-1}] \quad (7)$$

This transformation produces $N = n - n_{lags} - n_{steps} + 1$ pairs that can then be used for training and evaluating the models. In our case, due to the seasonality of the data, the lag window is set to $n_{lags} = 168$, representing a week of hourly data, while the forecast horizon was set to $n_{steps} = 24$, which corresponds to one full day.

PyTorch is used to create and train the MLP models and the input-output pairs are therefore converted to floating-point tensor pairs and loaded into a DataLoader object. This enables batch iteration during training and ensures efficient batch handling. A batch size of 32 is used for all experiments.

Fig. 5. The hierarchical structure of the office building considered in the case study.

The resulting dataset includes a collection of time series from each node of the hierarchy, where each series results in parallel sequences of X-Y pairs that are produced by the rolling-window approach. The series are temporally aligned, so that the dataset can be split into batches, enabling the simultaneous training of all models using shared batch iterations.

4.2. Model architecture

The models used share a common architecture, based on MLPs, as they can effectively handle time series data while offering great customization options [43]. The MLPs are tested with multiple configurations in order to identify the best-performing hyperparameter combination, in terms of forecasting accuracy on the validation set. The

Table 1
Hyperparameter values examined during the MLPs' tuning process.

Hyperparameter	Values examined
Hidden layer size	64, 128, 256, 512
Number of hidden layers	2, 3, 4
Learning rate	0.01, 0.001, 0.0001
Dropout rate	0.1, 0.2, 0.3
Batch size	16, 32, 64
Epochs	12, 25, 50, 100

experiments are conducted using a range of commonly adopted values for each hyperparameter, as detailed below:

The experiments yielded varying results. Deeper and larger hidden layers exhibited increased overfitting, necessitating the use of a dropout

Fig. 6. Example of energy consumption patterns across different hierarchical levels of the building, including the total building, individual sections, floors, and rooms.

layer. For this reason the optimal combination to mitigate overfitting consisted of three hidden layers of size 256 and a dropout rate of 0.2. Regarding the batch size, a size of 32 proved to be the most stable and produced accurate results throughout the training process. Moreover, increasing the number of epochs improved forecasting accuracy, but also significantly increased training time. Since the improvements became marginal after surpassing 25 epochs, they were fixed at 25 in order to maintain time and resource efficiency. The optimizer performed the best with a learning rate of 0.001 when fixing the number of epochs at 25. Lastly, the Adam optimizer was selected because it is a widely used optimization algorithm for MLPs and it is typical in time series forecasting applications due to faster convergence and better handling of non-stationary objectives [44,45].

The finalized baseline model consists of five different layers, with the following configuration:

- An input layer with linear transformation of dimension $d_{in} = 168$.
- Three fully connected hidden layers of dimension $d_{hidden} = 256$, each with ReLU activation and a Dropout layer in the middle to mitigate overfitting. The Dropout layer is initialized with a dropout rate of 0.2.
- An output layer with linear transformation of dimension $d_{out} = 24$.

A separate instance is initialized for each series, using the same naming convention as the time series in the data loaders. It should also be noted that the weights of all MLP layers are initialized using the Kaiming uniform method, as provided by PyTorch's default configuration. The Adam optimizer is initialized with the selected learning rate of 0.001

and the default parameters as set by PyTorch, which include $\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$, $\epsilon = 10^{-8}$, weight decay set to zero and without AMSGrad [46]. This configuration aims to provide consistency and high forecasting accuracy across all hierarchical levels.

4.3. Training setup

The selected setup allows the models to train in parallel and exchange information between optimization steps. The models are trained using mini-batch gradient descent and an Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001. The following process described refers to the lifetime of a single batch.

Initially, the base forecasts are produced using the models in training. It is important to note that the batch contains aligned data points from all m time series in order to allow simultaneous forward passes across all models. For each model, the predictions are then used to calculate the two components of the loss, L , namely the accuracy loss ($L_{Accuracy}$) and the coherence loss ($L_{Coherence}$). The accuracy loss is computed through MASE with $s = 24 \times 7 = 168$ to account for both the daily and weekly seasonality of the series. The coherence loss is then added to the accuracy loss, again using the MASE metric to ensure both losses are expressed in comparable scales, as described in Section 2. A weight factor, λ , can also be used to control the effect of the coherence loss, as follows:

$$L = L_{Accuracy} + \lambda \cdot L_{Coherence} \quad (8)$$

(a) Aggregated forecasts with Leaf-Oriented reconciliation.

(b) Aggregated forecasts with Closed-Loop Leaf-Oriented reconciliation.

(c) Aggregated forecasts with Root-Oriented reconciliation.

(d) Aggregated forecasts with Closed-Loop Root-Oriented reconciliation.

(e) Aggregated forecasts with Bi-Directional reconciliation.

(f) Aggregated forecasts with Closed-Loop Bi-Directional reconciliation.

Fig. 7. Aggregated results for each of the reconciliation methods applied. The time series are summed for each level of the hierarchy, in order to show the deviation between levels as well as the actual series.

Through empirical experimentation and considering the selected MLP hyperparameters, the λ factor is set to 0.5. This value is chosen in order to avoid the dominance of the coherence loss and instead ensure that the time series maintain their own unique trends and characteristics rather than overfitting to hierarchical coherence.

The overall batch loss is then obtained as the sum of all m individual losses, which is back-propagated after each pass through the shared Adam optimizer. Through this set-up, the gradient of each series incorporates both its individual accuracy error as well as the coherence feedback from the related nodes in the hierarchy. The joint optimization serves as the mechanism which enables information exchange among the series, providing an interconnected forecasting system that promotes global coherence.

4.4. Evaluation measures

To support the evaluation of the proposed approaches, two widely adopted error measures are considered, namely the Mean Squared Scaled Error (MSSE) and MASE. Because the study compares forecasts produced at different hierarchical levels, it is important to use scale-independent measures to ensure that performance is assessed properly regardless of the magnitude of each series [47]. Overall, these metrics provide a better understanding of the various aspects of forecast accuracy and enable scale-independent comparison among the different reconciliation methods.

4.5. Benchmarks

A Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (SARIMA) model combined with different traditional reconciliation methods is employed to generate individual forecasts. This model serves as a classical baseline and is well-suited for data with strong daily seasonality. The non-seasonal and seasonal orders are selected automatically by minimizing the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) on the training portion of each series [48], using the stepwise search in AutoARIMA [49]. The forecasts produced by the SARIMA model are subsequently reconciled using four reconciliation methods, namely the BU, TD, MO, and MinT [15]. The results for the base forecasts, as well as the different reconciliation methods are presented in Table 2 in the next section.

5. Results

Table 2 summarizes the accuracy of the proposed forecasting methods and the benchmarks based on the evaluation measures described above, across the four levels of the hierarchy. Starting with the benchmarks, they demonstrate satisfactory performance across all levels, with minor differences observed among the reconciliation methods employed. The BU and MO achieve slightly better results, especially at the bottom level, however, all methods provide a strong baseline for comparison.

Focusing on the customized models presented in this study, it is evident from the results that most of the reconciliation losses applied

Fig. 8. Comparison of SARIMA (unreconciled) and CL-LO method, showcasing the forecasting performance for the second floor in section B and the rooms included in it. The forecasted time series are shown together with the actual values for the day depicted.

exceeded the benchmarks and achieved substantial improvements across all levels. The custom reconciliation method $CL - LO$ achieved the best performance overall, particularly for levels zero, two, and three, where both metrics exhibited the lowest forecast errors in nearly all cases. In comparison, the $CL - BD$ achieved the best performance for level one, while remaining comparable to the previous model for the remaining levels as well, demonstrating strong and consistent results. The BD method also showed comparable performance, and even achieved the best MASE at level three and highest weighted average MASE together with $CL - BD$. Although less accurate overall, the LO also managed to surpass the established benchmarks, demonstrating solid performance despite not surpassing the top customized models.

While these four methods exceeded the benchmarks and performed very well, the RO and $CL - RO$ methods performed poorly and failed to surpass the benchmarks. This demonstrates that these models were unable to function effectively when all the sibling nodes were compared jointly against the parent node, and instead should be applied individually when calculating the coherence loss. This phenomenon likely occurs because these methods prioritize parent nodes and force child nodes to conform to them during optimization. More specifically, since the methods penalize discrepancies between the parent forecast and the sum of their children's forecasts, if the parent forecast is underestimated in the early epochs, the child forecasts are system-

atically pulled downward to minimize the coherence loss. This creates a cascading effect where underestimation propagates recursively through the hierarchy, leading to forecasts with worse accuracy and lower magnitudes.

The results are visualized in Fig. 7 and confirm the effectiveness of the approach presented in this study, demonstrating that the integrated reconciliation methodology can deliver accurate and coherent forecasts.

To further demonstrate the impact of the proposed approach on hierarchical coherence, an illustrative comparison between the base SARIMA forecasts (unreconciled) and the reconciled forecasts produced by the $CL - LO$ method is presented in Fig. 8. Specifically, the figure depicts the energy demand of the second floor in section B, together with the demand of its child nodes. Each subfigure presents the actual values together with the forecasts generated by both methods for the same day. It is evident that the forecasts produced by the $CL - LO$ method follow the actual load profiles more closely, while exhibiting improved alignment between the parent node (floor) and its children (rooms). This observation confirms the method's ability to enhance hierarchical coherence relative to unreconciled methods.

In order to complement the evaluation, alongside the average error measures, a Multiple Comparison with the Best (MCB) test is implemented to assess whether the observed differences between the methods are statistically significant [50]. MCB enables the comparison among

Fig. 9. MCB analysis results across the different hierarchy levels. Each plot compares all reconciliation methods against the best-performing one. The error bars represent a 95% confidence interval.

Fig. 10. Pairwise Relative Coherence Error (RCE) between different hierarchical levels across the proposed reconciliation methods.

reconciliation methods relative to the best performing one by constructing simultaneous confidence intervals for their differences. More specifically, a set of out-of-sample absolute errors at each forecast horizon is used and subsequently scaled into MASE values for each series and day. This results in a total of $N * M$ observations, where M is the number of unique series in each level of the hierarchy and N the number of fore-

casted values, which in this case is 24 (day-ahead). This approach treats each day of the forecasts as a replication, thus increasing the number of observations per reconciliation method and allowing the confidence intervals to tighten, ultimately enhancing the reliability of the test.

The results of the MCB analysis are presented in Fig. 9. At level 1, the $CL - LO$ method achieved the best performance, with the lowest mean

Table 2

Forecasting accuracy of the proposed forecasting methods and benchmarks across the four hierarchical levels (plus overall and weighted average). The top-performing method of each column is highlighted in bold.

Method	Level 0	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Avg.	Wtd Avg.
MASE						
LO	0.740	0.610	0.822	0.800	0.743	0.781
RO	3.349	2.951	2.151	1.562	2.503	1.801
BD	0.587	0.538	0.764	0.787	0.669	0.757
CL-LO	0.569	0.540	0.738	0.801	0.662	0.775
CL-RO	2.725	2.621	1.712	1.293	2.088	1.582
CL-BD	0.640	0.485	0.771	0.804	0.675	0.757
Base SARIMA	0.844	0.891	0.856	0.916	0.877	0.900
Benchmark - BU	0.770	0.765	0.809	0.817	0.790	0.813
Benchmark - MO	0.758	0.756	0.837	0.847	0.799	0.822
Benchmark - MT	0.831	0.808	0.840	1.160	0.910	1.064
Benchmark - TD	0.844	0.819	0.851	1.027	0.885	0.990
MSSE						
LO	0.192	0.219	0.333	0.312	0.264	0.308
RO	4.097	3.523	1.968	1.164	2.688	1.657
BD	0.152	0.172	0.295	0.311	0.232	0.292
CL-LO	0.126	0.175	0.270	0.285	0.214	0.280
CL-RO	2.742	2.703	1.243	0.771	1.865	1.306
CL-BD	0.147	0.130	0.299	0.323	0.225	0.296
Base SARIMA	0.233	0.296	0.319	0.404	0.313	0.378
Benchmark - BU	0.234	0.286	0.299	0.306	0.281	0.302
Benchmark - MO	0.225	0.280	0.310	0.323	0.284	0.308
Benchmark - MT	0.212	0.263	0.287	0.535	0.324	0.476
Benchmark - TD	0.214	0.270	0.303	0.448	0.309	0.394

MASE and statistically outperforming several of the other methods. The *BD* and *CL - BD* methods followed closely, while the *LO* method showed no statistically significant deviation from the best-performing method. Notably, the *RO* and *CL - RO* methods exhibited the largest and statistically significant discrepancies, as expected given the results in *Table 2*.

Levels 2 and 3 show similar results, with the *CL - LO* method achieving the best performance, while the *BD*, *CL - BD* and *LO* methods follow closely, showing only minor statistical differences. The *RO* and *CL - RO* methods continue to perform significantly worse at these levels. Finally, at level 4, which is the most granular, the *CL - BD*, *BD* and *LO* methods performed the best, while the *CL - LO* also performed well with a minor difference. The same behaviour as in previous levels is observed for the *CL - RO* and *RO* methods.

As concluded by the MCB procedure, the results remain consistent across all levels and align with the findings of *Table 2*. Overall, the *CL - LO* method has the best performance at upper levels, whereas *CL - BD* performs the best at lower, disaggregated levels. The results reinforce the robustness and consistent performance of both methods across the hierarchy. On the other hand, the *CL - RO* and *RO* methods, as expected from the previous observations, consistently show poor accuracy and appear unsuitable for producing accurate forecasts.

While forecasting accuracy is essential to ensure reliable and trustworthy results, it is equally important to consider the coherence between the different levels of the hierarchy. To quantify this, an additional metric is introduced: the Relative Coherence Error (RCE). RCE is a scale-independent metric that measures the average relative difference between a parent node and the sum of its children, expressed in a percentage-like error. A lower RCE indicates a higher degree of coherence in the hierarchical forecast. This metric enables a comprehensive assessment of the consistency between the different levels of the hierarchy, and thus evaluates the effectiveness of the applied coherence losses. The RCE is computed as follows:

$$RCE = \frac{1}{|P|} \sum_{p \in P} \left| \frac{\hat{y}_p - \sum_i \hat{y}_{c_i}}{\hat{y}_p + \epsilon} \right| \tag{9}$$

Where *P* is the set of parent nodes in the hierarchy, \hat{y}_p is the forecast of the parent node *p*, \hat{y}_{c_i} are the child forecasts and ϵ is a small constant added to avoid division by zero.

The results are presented in *Fig. 10*, showing the pairwise RCE across all combinations of hierarchical levels. It is evident that among the different reconciliation methods, the *CL - LO* method yields the most consistent and lowest coherence errors. The *BD* method also performs closely, with slightly higher errors in pairs involving level 1, yet overall demonstrates consistent coherence across the hierarchy. In contrast, the *RO* method exhibits the largest discrepancies in coherence, with errors reaching 17.52% between levels 0 and 3, indicating that the reconciliation was ineffective when propagating from higher to lower levels. On the other hand, the *CL - RO* method managed to achieve significant improvement in most pairs, with better coherence between the top and bottom levels, demonstrating that the closed loop approach provided better results in terms of reconciliation. Finally, the *CL - BD* and *LO* methods delivered average results, with higher errors in pairs involving the root level.

These results highlight that while forecasting accuracy is high for multiple reconciliation methods, the *CL - LO* method managed to outperform the others in providing reconciled and structurally consistent forecasts.

To summarize, the results collected so far indicate that the *CL - LO* approach outperformed the other methods. More specifically, it delivered the highest accuracy across the majority of the levels while also achieving the lowest RCE, confirming that the forecasts were both accurate and hierarchically consistent. The *CL - LO* method uses the leaf nodes as the main reference for coherence, which allows it to focus on the details available at such granular levels, providing better accuracy, especially at lower levels. In addition, the closed-loop approach provides circularity of the information exchange, which leads to better coherence. The *CL - BD* on the other hand, demonstrates higher accuracy and coherence at intermediate levels, which reflects its strength in integrating information from upper and lower levels. However, at the root level, its performance was worse than at other levels, suggesting that the additional circular feedback between upper and lower nodes may occasionally introduce minor inconsistencies at the top of the hierarchy. The *BD* method on the other hand, did not surpass the other methods in accuracy for the majority of levels but still performed closely and provided balanced coherence errors throughout the hierarchy. While its coherence errors were higher than those of the *CL - LO*, it is important to note that unlike the *CL - BD*, which struggled to adjust the root level correctly, it provided stable results across all levels.

Overall, these observations suggest that the closed-loop regularization framework enables strong accuracy-coherence synergy, with *CL - LO* offering the best global performance, *CL - BD* excelling at mid-level accuracy, and *BD* providing consistent coherence across the hierarchy.

6. Conclusion and future work

This study introduces and evaluates a novel, ML-based reconciliation approach that can enhance the accuracy and coherence for hierarchical energy forecasting in complex buildings. The proposed methodology dynamically integrates the reconciliation process into model training by designing loss functions that promote structural coherence, and enabling multiple models to train together and exchange information. This collaborative framework contributes to the ultimate goal of generating coherent forecasts across a building’s hierarchical structure, thereby supporting effective energy management of buildings to meet energy efficiency standards and reduce emissions.

Specifically, the *CL - LO* method surpassed the best-performing benchmark (BU) method by 16% in MASE and up to 24% in MSSE, with the most significant improvements observed at higher hierarchical levels. This method also exhibited strong hierarchical coherence compared to other methods, achieving the most stable results for all levels. Taking

into account that the office building used in the case study consumes an average of 912 kWh per weekday, these statistical findings correspond to an average decrease of 22 kWh in forecast error per weekday compared to the benchmark methods. This improvement, especially for the top levels of the hierarchy, provides a significant advantage to building and facility managers, since it enables them to perform more precise load shifting during peak hours and thus, further improve grid stability and reduce electricity costs by approximately 2.4%. In addition, more accurate forecasts at granular levels enable the optimization of HVAC schedules, which can enhance occupant comfort on the one hand, and allow better utilization of on-site renewable generation and storage on the other. These findings support the use of the *CL – LO* method for real-world deployment in energy forecasting applications.

The significance of our methodology extends to the broader energy and built environment sectors, by contributing to areas of energy efficiency and building management. Accurate and coherent multi-level energy forecasts provide the foundation for optimizing energy usage in buildings and enable more granular and responsive control. Moreover, reliable forecasts at aggregated and disaggregated levels form the foundation for sophisticated strategies such as predictive maintenance and control, fault detection and load shifting, all aimed at enhancing the building's operational efficiency and minimizing energy waste. In addition, hierarchical forecasts can facilitate the identification of underperforming areas within buildings and guide targeted improvements that maximize energy performance and contribute to broader decarbonization goals.

Our study indicates potential avenues to refine future research and address the issues encountered. A primary option is to apply the method on different types of buildings – residences, companies, and factories – located in different climate zones and assess whether its performance remains similar under the various scenarios tested. Another option is to implement the latest building automation systems, allowing for real-world validation and identification of operational constraints and benefits. A further direction is to extend the method into probabilistic forecasting settings to support decisions in applications where estimating uncertainty is critical, such as energy management and demand response.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Daniela Stoian: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization; **Evangelos Spiliotis:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization; **Efstathios Stamatopoulos:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation; **Elissaios Sarmas:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration; **Vangelis Marinakis:** Supervision.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The work presented is based on research conducted within the framework of the Horizon Europe European Commission projects DigiBUILD (Grant Agreement No. 101069658) and DATAWiSE (Grant Agreement No. 101147855). The authors would like to thank all the DigiBUILD and DATAWiSE consortium partners for their fruitful discussions, remarks and observations. Additionally, we extend our gratitude to Petteri Rekoma from Forum Virium Helsinki for preparing and providing the

building data used in the Finland case study. The content of the paper is the sole responsibility of its authors and does not necessarily reflect the views of the EC.

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